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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“EXTREME WEATHER EVENTS, MENTAL HEALTH, AND FILIPINO RESILIENCE”

For the past two weeks, the Philippines has been battered by three typhoons, namely, Crising, Dante, and Emong. The country is currently experiencing extreme weather events, which have caused suspension of classes and work, damage to property, and loss of life. According to the National Aeronautics and Space Administration or NASA (2024), the increase in frequency of extreme weather events, such as stronger and stronger typhoons battering the Philippines, is caused by greenhouse gases primarily through the burning of fossil fuels. These greenhouse gases act like a blanket, trapping heat and thus warming the planet. As temperatures increase, it negatively affects the water cycle and weather patterns, causing extreme weather events.

On the other hand, according to Haase (2023), there is a strong connection between extreme weather events and mental health. Individuals affected by extreme weather events may experience stress, insomnia, problematic coping behaviors, and mental disorders such as major depression, anxiety, and symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder. Thus, psychosocial support and preparedness are important to mitigate the mental health challenges posed by extreme weather events. In this regard, Filipinos have been glamorized to be resilient. Enduring despite the difficulties it faced, especially from natural disasters and calamities. We can see positive depictions of this resilience in television, radio, and social media. Yet, the promotion of Filipino resilience is hiding persistent and systematic corruption and inefficiencies of government. Instead of promoting Filipino resilience, people should make our leaders accountable for the failure in mitigating the effects of extreme weather conditions because of corruption of public funds in infrastructure projects and incompetence in implementing much-needed programs. Hence, as the country is being battered again by many typhoons, may Filipinos open their eyes to the truth that instead of accepting the glamorization of resilience, they demand accountability to people in power to improve systems which are meant to protect us.

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